

Towards a Definition of Critical AI Literacy: Three Interdependent Concepts and Their Functions

There are many definitions of critical AI literacy, each foregrounding different elements depending on context, perspectives, theoretical references (Rapanta et al., 2025). However, across most of these definitions, three interdependent concepts recur. The purpose of this short entry is to show how these concepts function within a definition of critical AI literacy.

The first concept, *AI literacy*, indicates what the **domain** in question is. While AI literacy in itself is a fluid definition (Velandar et al., 2024), it usually refers to a set of competencies to understand what AI systems are, how they work and how to use them (Long & Magerko, 2020; Ng et al., 2021).

If AI literacy is the domain, *critical* is how human thinking approaches it and indicates the interrogative **stance** we take towards AI literacy: whether in educational, sociopolitical, professional, or other contexts, it involves actively questioning, interrogating the power relations AI systems encode, evaluating their claims and harms, and retaining the right to use them carefully (Conrad & Kamperman, 2025), or refuse them (McQuillan, 2022). The third concept draws on Freire's *critical literacy* (Freire, 1970; Bali, 2023; Critical AI Literacy, 2025) and is the **framework** that dialectically brings the previous two elements together, turning the interrogation into action and purpose: developing critical consciousness (*conscientização*) of how AI systems participate in and reproduce structures of inequality; engaging in ongoing cycles of reflection and action (*praxis*) aimed at transforming those structures; and recognising that this is a collective, situated, dynamic and political

practice, not a stable set of individual skills to be acquired.

Critical AI literacy could therefore be described as an ongoing, situated practice of reflection and action through which individuals and communities question and evaluate AI systems and the conditions that give rise to them, and, as result of informed analysis, choose when to use, resist, transform, or refuse them.

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